

Report

Music and Majesty: Chapels Royal, Cathedrals, and Colleges, c.1485–1688, 1–2
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Music and Majesty, organised by Katie Bank, Oscar Patton, and Samuel Teague, was an organisational and academic triumph. The conference gathered musicologists, historians, and scholars working on various aspects of musical foundations and institutions. The time period covered ranged from Henry Tudor's usurpation to the Glorious Revolution, addressing an era in which musical and liturgical fashions were in constant flux. This event revealed the depth of scholarship in this area, exhibiting the work of both seasoned and more junior researchers.

The conference opened with a panel titled 'Projecting Majesty' in which all presenters focused on landmark moments of change in the seventeenth century. William Hunt spoke on the politically charged musical borrowing in Edmund Hooper's verse-anthem *O God of Gods* dedicated to James I. Hooper's quotation of Byrd appears to have sparked a small musical tradition, with a simple four-note figure on the text 'who peace and joy' recurring in works by Gibbons, Tomkins, and Ward. This may provide evidence that composers of the era set the texts of their verse-anthems with either their own or their patrons' political desires in mind. Kenneth Fincham then spoke about the impact of the Caroline settlement, highlighting how Charles II, used it as a forum to express his liturgical preferences. Owen Rees concluded the session by discussing the influence of Catherine of Braganza, Charles II's Portuguese consort, and the role of Portuguese sacred music at the Restoration court. Building on a lifetime of research into Portuguese polyphony, Rees addressed Samuel Pepys's changing opinions on the music of Catherine's chapel, as recorded in his famous diaries.

The second panel of the day focused on music for special occasions. Matthais Range presented a paper on the role of the Supreme Governor of the Church of England, created during the Henrician Reformation, and its evolution throughout the rest of the so-called 'Long Reformation' (c. 1540s-1700). Range's paper studied observable trends through the lens of music for special occasions. Alexandra Siso delivered an intriguing paper on musical settings of the *Lamentations of Jeremiah* and the Royal Maundy, during which Elizabeth I washed the feet of poor women in imitation of Christ at the Last Supper, portraying herself as a princess of Jerusalem. Further research is needed on settings of the *Lamentations* by English composers. While Siso's presentation rightly focused on Tallis's famous setting, other composers set different portions of the text. For example, the text of John Mundy's setting is a patchwork, combining the original incipit, Hebrew letters, Psalm 121 (Vulgate), and prayers against schism. Consequently, a variety of allegorical interpretations can be drawn from different settings of the *Lamentations*. Anthony Musson presented the first of two papers on the AHRC-funded project *Henry VIII on Tour*, examining the institutional and personal networks formed and

their reputational impact while “on tour.”

This panel was followed by a session examining physical spaces, with two of the papers focusing on the Scottish Chapels Royal. Charlie Spragg spoke about the newly-constructed chapel of James VI at Stirling Castle, the first purpose-built Reformed church in Scotland. Spragg highlighted how the architect of the chapel, William Schaw, drew direct proportional parallels to King Solomon's temple, invoking desirable allegorical associations. David Coney discussed the liturgical and musical revival at the Scottish Chapel Royal. The Calvinist influence manifested primarily in hostility towards imagery, less so towards architecture, vestments, and music. A limited musical revival began in the 1580s, though most appointees to the Chapel were courtiers, leading to a potential variability in its musical competency. Mark Kirby took a broader view, examining different ranks of chapels (royal, aristocratic, collegiate, parish) and the intellectual processes underpinning these distinctions. Kirby particularly focused on how the concept of ‘decorum’ in architecture and how this realised the ideals of the Early Modern chapel, many of which were described as “comely” and “decent.”

After a wine and canapé reception, a special service was held at St James's Palace, the formal base of the Royal Court, with a program covering the entire gamut of the conference. The ambitious repertoire was sung by the choir of HM Chapel Royal, St James's Palace, providing an enduring link between the institution studied at the conference and the modern incarnation.

The second day commenced with a panel examining sources, their use, and pedagogy. Daniel Koplitz discussed the challenges faced by those studying the repertoire of the Tudor Chapel Royal due to the paucity of sixteenth century sources. Their paper examined the repertoire and activity of St Laurence's church, Ludlow. Despite the distance of Ludlow from the centres of royal musicking (chiefly London), the Ludlow Partbooks are one of several surviving sets of music from the Welsh Marches, including the Chirk Castle Partbooks (near Oswestry) and the Drexel Partbooks (likely from Gloucestershire). Katie McKeogh examined the survival of liturgical books in England's universities. Books in libraries were treated differently from those in chapels, and ownership did not necessarily imply agreement. McKeogh considered these factors and explored what these survivals reveal about the aural landscape and liturgical change. In particularly focusing on the meanings these books acquired once removed from chapels and placed in college libraries. Katherine Butler concluded the session with a paper on the use of catches, rounds, and canons in chorister education. Much like in primary music education today, such songs were used to teach young children to sing. For Renaissance choristers, these songs also taught composition and how to form cadences. So important were catches and rounds to chorister pedagogy that they were one of the first skills taught after solmization.

The penultimate panel examined the impact of ideological preferences on the music and worship of the Chapel Royal. Jonathan Arnold discussed Humanist critiques of music and musicians, noting how Humanist scholars viewed music as a powerful rhetorical tool to convey the meaning of sung texts and enhance listeners' understanding of these texts. However, these ideals sometimes manifested as hostility towards polyphonic singing. Arnold cited Desiderius Erasmus's famous complaint that English monks spent too much time learning to sing, their singing could not be understood, and the singers could not contemplate what they were singing. This problem, as Erasmus saw it, was perhaps a long ailment for English choristers: Geoffrey Chaucer, writing over a century previous in *The Prioresses Tale*, describes a seven year old boy who despite knowing ‘the firste vers koude al by rote [The first verse en-

tirely by heart]’, ‘Noght wiste he what this Latyn was to seye’ [He knew not what this Latin meant]. Andrew Foster then spoke about the musical preferences and investments of Archbishop Richard Neile, whose fifty-year career included the Deanery of Westminster and six bishoprics, including the archbishopric of York. Neile, Foster noted, would have been popular with modern church musicians - he raised choir wages, improved food quality, and helped provide new organs for the Chapel of Henry VII, Westminster Abbey, and the cathedrals of Durham and York. Nicholas Thistlethwaite closed the panel with a fascinating paper proposing that the provisions made for organs, and the varying fates of these instruments in churches, chapels, and cathedrals reflected broader societal changes (or a ‘barometer of change’) during the Reformation(s).

The final session focused on the mobility of musicians and the Chapel Royal. Magnus Williamson presented preliminary findings from the *Henry VIII on Tour* project, highlighting pre-Reformation musical foundations along the River Nene and how town-music relationships required strong musical institutions. Williamson also discussed how royal progresses facilitated musical dissemination and the logistical expenses of taking the royal chapel ‘on tour’. Lucy Munro examined the interrelationship between the Chapel Royal and the theatre, discussing the system of deputies appointed by William Hunnis and Nathaniel Giles to manage choristers’ musical tuition and play performances. Kerry McCarthy concluded the conference with a paper on how Chapel Royal musicians travelled. McCarthy shared how in 1544, ‘Gentleman Singers’ were provided with an ‘allowance of a cart for the carriage of their stuff’. The singers likely carried considerable “stuff” with them including musical instruments, clothing, and manuscripts (all of which are heavy!).

The conference concluded with remarks by Peter McCullough, who reflected on several recurring themes. These included the contrast between what was *supposed* to be, and what actually occurred, as well as the extensive musical provisions made for noble and royal households beyond the monarchy. McCullough dramatically presented an extraordinary archival discovery, which greatly excited the conference delegates and will no doubt be fully explored in due course.

The conference organisers deserve commendation for their efforts. *Music and Majesty* demonstrated the vitality of research on all aspects of musical institutions in the fifteenth, sixteenth, and seventeenth centuries. The cross-disciplinary nature of the event was particularly pleasing. I eagerly anticipate any outputs that result from this conference.